

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D6.6 Research design: Community and citizen responses - update M28

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an update of the research design of work package 6. As such, it offers methodological guidance to partners involved in the work package, summarising the research process to date and describing the additional data collection necessary for the successful completion of the work package. Work package 6 contributes to all of the COVINFORM project-level research questions, with an emphasis on how local contexts have shaped COVID-19 impacts and responses. Based on desk research on selected municipalities within the COVINFORM target countries, as well as a review of relevant scientific literature, the WP6 team developed five sub-questions focused on this topic:

- **RQ5.1. Locus:** How did spatial system conditions and spatialised practices mediate COVID-19 impacts and responses in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.2. Social ties:** How did social networks mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.3. Joint action:** What roles have CSOs, grassroots initiatives, and residents played in the provision of health and social services in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.4. Sharing:** How did shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.5. Intra-community diversity:** How did intra-community patterns of difference mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

We have sought to answer these questions through interviews with representatives of civil society organisations (CSOs) active in the research sites. During the initial fieldwork period (February through May 2022), N=38 of N=50 planned interviews were completed. These served as the basis for the findings reported in deliverables *D6.3 Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impact* and *D6.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts*.

Those partners who did not achieve their full sample during the first fieldwork period have continued conducting interviews, with the aim of reaching the full sample of N=50 by early summer 2023. This should allow all findings to be reported in the forthcoming deliverable *D6.7 Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impact – update M34*.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
CSO	Civil society organisation
GO	Governmental organisation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
RQ	Research question
SESF	Social-Ecological Systems Framework

1 Introduction

This document (D6.6) provides methodological guidance to partners involved in WP6, summarising the research process to date and describing the additional data collection necessary for the successful completion of the work package. The data collection focuses on the following questions:

- **RQ5.1. Locus:** How did spatial system conditions and spatialised practices mediate COVID-19 impacts and responses in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.2. Social ties:** How did social networks mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.3. Joint action:** What roles have CSOs, grassroots initiatives, and residents played in the provision of health and social services in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.4. Sharing:** How did shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.5. Intra-community diversity:** How did intra-community patterns of difference mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

A template for reporting newly collected data is furthermore provided.

2 Overview of empirical research

2.1 Aims and objectives

The COVINFORM project addresses the following top-level research questions, within the target countries and municipalities, across several work packages:

- **RQ1:** How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- **RQ2:** How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- **RQ3:** What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response of certain vulnerable groups?
- **RQ4:** What were the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?
- **RQ5:** What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

Work package 6 contributes insight from a civil society perspective to all four questions. Based on desk research on diverse local contexts presented in D6.1, as well as a review of the literature on “community” presented in D6.2, we developed corollaries to RQ5 on local contexts (D6.2, pg. 28-30). Five sub-questions in particular stand out, insofar as they intersect with the “elements of community” identified by public health researchers MacQueen et al. (2001):

- **RQ5.1. Locus:** How did spatial system conditions and spatialised practices mediate COVID-19 impacts and responses in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.2. Social ties:** How did social networks mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.3. Joint action:** What roles have CSOs, grassroots initiatives, and residents played in the provision of health and social services in the sub-national research sites?

- **RQ5.4. Sharing:** How did shared attitudes, beliefs, and practices mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?
- **RQ5.5. Intra-community diversity:** How did intra-community patterns of difference mediate COVID-19 impacts in the sub-national research sites?

As described in Section 3 below, these research questions were used as the basis for the CSO representative interview topic guide, as well as for the analysis of the transcripts.

2.2 Target population and sampling

Each WP6 research partner was asked to conduct **N≥5** interviews with representatives of civil society organisations (CSOs) active in COVID-19 responses or related activities in the target research site. No quotas were set for types of organisations; rather, an appropriate sample was selected by each partner in discourse with SINUS. Representatives of both established CSOs and grassroots initiatives established in response to the pandemic were sought. The following a best-effort sociodemographic criteria were furthermore suggested to help ensure a balanced sample:

Table 1. Sampling criteria for CSO representatives – best-effort basis

Criteria	
Representative of a CSO established before the COVID-19 pandemic	N≥1
Representative of a CSO or grassroots initiative/action established during the COVID-19 pandemic	N≥1
Self-identifies as female	N≥2
Works directly with vulnerable groups	N≥2
Self-identifies as a member of a vulnerable group	N≥1

Due to challenges explained in Section 3.2.1 below, a total of N=38 interviews (rather than the planned N=50) were achieved by May 2022. These were used as the basis for the analysis conducted in D6.3 and D6.4.

Since May 2022, partners have continued to recruit respondents and conduct interviews, with the aim of filling the target sample of N=50 in time to report updated findings in D6.7 and D6.8. Table 1 presents the current recruiting status:

Table 2. Overview of WP6 expert interviews

Partner	Research site	Number of interviews
SYNYO	Austria (Vienna)	N=4
UANTWERPEN	Belgium (Brussels)	N=5
SINUS	Germany (Mannheim)	N=5
KEMEA	Greece (Athens)	N=5
SAPIENZA	Italy (Rome)	N=4
FS	Portugal (Lisbon)	N=5
URJC	Spain (Madrid)	N=5

UGOT	Sweden (Gothenburg)	N=5
TRI	England (Birmingham area)	N=3
SU	Wales (Swansea area)	N=4
Total		N=45

Note here that in addition to the CSO representative interviews, the remaining WP6 deliverables will draw to some extent on the resident interviews conducted across WP4-7. Details on the resident interviews have been reported in D3.6.

3 Methodological reflections

3.1 Theoretical and methodological basis

The theoretical foundation for WP6 was grounded on a thorough literature review on the concept of “community” in sociology and public health research (see D6.2, Section 3.1). The approach taken by public health researchers MacQueen et al. (2001) was particularly inspirational to the research team, insofar as it was grounded in empirical research on perceptions of “community” among members of diverse communities of identity and practice. Asking their respondents “what does community mean to you?”, MacQueen et al. identified five fundamental “elements of community”: “locus”, “sharing”, “action”, “[social] ties”, and “diversity” (pg. 1931). A second round of literature review was conducted to clarify the role of these “elements of community” in COVID-19 impacts and responses on a local level. It was determined that all five elements played a key role in determining or mediating COVID-19 outcomes in sites worldwide, including several of the target countries (see D6.2, Section 3.2).

Based on these literature reviews, WP-specific research questions were derived from the project-level research questions (see D6.2, Section 4). The interview topic guide – which is presented in D6.2, Annex 2 – operationalises these questions. A variation on the Problem-Centred Interview format (PCI) (Witzel 2000) was used: Döringer’s “PCI expert interview” (2021), which progresses from a narrative opening account to a more structured exploration of the research questions. Mirroring MacQueen et al., the opening question was “What does the word ‘community’ mean to you?” The topic guide then investigated the following topics:

- Local baseline conditions and COVID-19 impact timeline
 - The research site before COVID-19
 - Vulnerability in the research site
 - CSOs in the research site
 - COVID-19 impact timeline
 - Prior to the first lockdowns
 - When the first lockdowns were introduced
 - When the first lockdowns were lifted
- Local COVID-19 responses
 - Health and social services
 - Overall evaluation and gaps
 - Roles of government, community organisations, and residents
 - Comparison to other neighbourhoods

- Risk communications
 - Overall evaluation and gaps
 - Appropriateness to social and cultural context
- Vaccination campaigns
 - Overall evaluation
 - Communication about campaigns
- Concluding questions
 - Drawbacks
 - Positive impacts or instances
 - Changes to the community

Additionally, interview participants were asked to fill in the standard WP4-7 sociodemographic questionnaire. With the consent of the participants, the interviews were recorded and transcribed, and memos were taken.

3.2 The research process to date

3.2.1 Recruiting and accompanying challenges

Between February and March 2022, partners recruited and conducted interviews. Each partner began by assembling a list of CSOs active in their target sub-national research site, then assessed the candidate organisations for relevance with regard to participation in COVID-19 responses and contact with vulnerable groups. Deadlines were set for status updates, to allow SINUS to double-check the proposed samples and monitor recruiting progress (see D6.3, Section 2.3.2).

Due to recruiting challenges detailed below, by the end of March 2022, a total of 38 interviews were conducted across nine of the ten intended target sites (76% of the target of N=50). Those partners who managed to conduct N≥3 interviews conducted an analysis guided by a standardised template (see D6.2, Annex 3). The country analyses were collected and used as the basis for D6.3, a compilation of country reports followed by a comparative discussion, as well as D6.4, which synthesises the findings within the context of the COVINFORM vulnerability assessment model (WP2) and the social-ecological systems framework (WP3).

As mentioned, the recruiting process saw more difficulty than anticipated. The first challenge that impacted recruiting was that relatively few partners had existing contacts with relevant CSOs in their target research sites, nor with gatekeeper organisations capable of recruiting such CSOs. As a result, the means of recruiting was often direct, “cold” outreach to the target CSOs. The second challenge was the impact of the successive crises of the COVID-19 pandemic and the war against Ukraine, as well as the extended and complex social, economic, and psychological impacts of both. As the COVINFORM project has recognised from its onset, such crises often have especially harmful effects on individuals and groups that are already vulnerable – and by extension, also on individuals and institutions that provide services and support to the vulnerable. Both crises also had impacts on the health and psychological wellbeing of the research team. Considering the challenge of cold outreach to overburdened practitioners amidst successive crises, recruiting progressed relatively smoothly: several CSO representatives interviewed by partners perceived the project as an opportunity to explain their experiences, assessments, and recommendations for the future to both the scientific community and policymakers. As of Winter 2023, all partners anticipate that they will be able to complete their remaining interviews.

Another, more specific challenge was that it proved difficult to reach the planned sample of $N \geq 1$ representative per site of a grassroots initiative/action established during the COVID-19 pandemic. The decentralised status of such initiatives (many are online platforms) also complicated outreach, as some partners could not find an appropriate point of contact, or perceived this as meaning that the initiatives were less locally relevant than CSOs with a physical presence in the target research site. This challenge was mitigated by focusing the second round of WP6 desk research specifically on grassroots initiatives and participatory practices. The findings are reported in D6.5.

3.2.2 Fieldwork, analysis, and reporting

The interviews themselves progressed well in all research sites. The CSO representatives interviewed worked on levels ranging from founding management to first-line staff, and represented a wide range of CSOs, including organisations providing material support (e.g., housing, food, etc.); physical and psychological health services; women's services; children's, youth, and family services; services oriented toward refugees and other migrants; services oriented toward ethnic and linguistic minority populations; etc. Most of the CSOs represented provided multiple types of service. The CSOs ranged in size from neighbourhood organisations to multinational organisations. Both secular and religious organisations were represented.

The transcripts were summarised by the interviewing partners using a standardised findings template (see D6.2, Annex 3). The template consisted of information about each interviewee, a brief summary of each individual interview, and a description of the findings of all interviews with regard to the key sections of the topic guide (see above). The findings per country were reviewed by SINUS and used as the basis for reporting the findings per country in D6.3, Section 3. When necessary, SINUS reached out to specific partners to resolve unclear information or fill gaps. An initial cross-country comparative analysis and discussion was given in D6.3, Section 4. This analysis was significantly expanded in D6.4, which situates the cross-country findings within two project-level theoretical frameworks: the COVINFORM vulnerability assessment model (developed in WP2) and the social-ecological systems framework.

3.2.3 Ethical considerations

Ethical and privacy implications were considered throughout recruiting and research, especially with regard to CSO representatives who themselves also identified as belonging to vulnerable groups. Guidelines provided in deliverables *D1.4 Ethical Framework*, in *D10.1 H - Requirement No. 1* (concerning measures to protect vulnerable groups and minimise the risk of their stigmatization as well as concerning possible incidental findings) and in *D10.2 H - Requirement No. 2* (informed consent procedures) were followed. National regulations on Ethics Committee approvals/opinions were furthermore abided by.

3.3 Next steps

3.3.1 Remaining interviews

As of Winter 2023, five interviews remain to be conducted:

Table 3. Overview of remaining WP6 expert interviews

Partner	Research site	Number of interviews
SYNYO	Austria (Vienna)	N=1

SAPIENZA	Italy (Rome)	N=1
TRI	England (Birmingham area)	N=2
SU	Wales (Swansea area)	N=1
Total		N=5

SINUS is in contact with the respective partners, and it is highly likely that the remaining interviews will be successfully conducted in time to report the findings in D6.7 and D6.8.

3.3.2 Analysis

Empirical research presented in deliverables across WP4-7 will be analysed according to the themes of their WPs and the research teams' expertise. There is also a common framework for analysis spanning all for WPs and domains. This enables the COVINFORM project to discuss findings across WPs.

4 Conclusions

WP6 contributes to all of the COVINFORM project-level research questions, with a particular emphasis on *RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts*. Based on desk research on local responses in selected municipalities within the COVINFORM target countries and a literature review of relevant theories of community, the WP6 team developed several sub-questions, which we have sought to answer through interviews with representatives of civil society organisations (CSOs) active in the research sites. Due to recruiting challenges, N=38 of the planned N=50 interviews were conducted during the initial fieldwork period ending in May 2022. These served as the basis for the findings reported in D6.3 and D6.4. Fieldwork has continued since, with N=45 interviews having been achieved by February 2023. The remaining five interviews are currently on track to be completed in time for all findings to be reported in D6.7 and D6.8. In addition to outlining procedures, this deliverable provides an updated template with which partners can summarise the findings of all interviews conducted since the last reporting deadline of May 2022.

References

Literature

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